

ECONOMY

MAIN PROFESSIONAL ROLES OF THE HR MANAGER

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Abstract

The formation of forms of joint creative activity is associated with the transformation of historically preceding forms of organizing joint activities: jointly consistent, jointly interacting, and jointly individual. It is in this sequence that in the twentieth century, as the experience of management of various organizations in developed countries shows, the development of fundamental forms of joint creative activity takes place. This process, if considered within the framework of the organizational and cultural approach, can be interpreted as the phases of the formation of a participatory organizational culture, and the transformations that the bureaucratic, organic, and entrepreneurial cultures underwent consistently generated paradigms of personnel work in the management of capitalist countries.

Keywords: Professional roles, Personal management, Management service, Consumer Motivation.

Introduction. If we use competence models about the very characteristics of the HR manager, then it is clear from all the above that it can be neither a one-dimensional model describing a fairly simple type of activity, nor an abstract model that serves as a generalization of the properties of a whole class of related activities. It should be a model of a complex organized activity that includes other types of activities as elements. Therefore, the HR manager competence model is a multi-role professional profile.

Discussion. What should be considered when developing a professional HR manager profile?

When creating a multi-role professional profile of an HR manager, you need to identify:

- ongoing and predictable trends in the future (in the organization of business, industry, market environment, engineering, and technology) that can significantly affect the functional characteristics of the HR manager;
- many key "areas of responsibility" of the HR manager;
- the most important tasks and results of work from the point of view of the HR manager himself;
- criteria for the effectiveness of its activities for each key function;
- the constructed block of basic abilities and other skills required to perform each key function and achieve the result of the HR manager's activity;
- specific behavior for the HR manager's activity shows his competence.

Based on the vision of the future of HR services and based on the experience of successful corporations, you can identify key roles for the profession of an HR manager.

1. **"HR strategist"** — a member of the management team responsible for developing and implementing the HR strategy, as well as organizational mechanisms for its support; management, and management systems for services performing the functions of HR management (Vice President for HR Management).

2. **"Head HR Management Service"** — organizer of the work of HR departments.

3. **"HR technologist"** — a developer and implementer of creative approaches in areas of activity specific to the HR manager, competent in special and technological knowledge, able to attract a variety of internal and external resources and use them effectively, taking into account the business prospects of the organization (head of the organizational development or personnel development service).

4. **"Personnel innovator"** — a manager, leader—or developer of experimental, initiative, or pilot projects that require a lot of attention and careful study before they are widely used in the practice of personnel management of the organization.

5. **"Executor"** — a specialist who implements operational personnel policy.

6. **"HR consultant"** (external or internal) — a professional who uses a panoramic vision of the corporation's prospects, practical knowledge in the field of human resource management, and expert skills to identify needs, opportunities, and ways to solve problems related to the development of organizational and human resources potential;

Researchers proposed many characteristics of the HR manager's competence, and 11 areas of competence were recognized as key, since they were included in expert assessments of all six mentioned HR manager roles. These 11 key areas of competence were grouped into three groups.

Personal decency

1. Ethics — respect for individual rights, responsibility for promises made, reliability, honesty, and fairness.

2. Conscientiousness — high demands on the results of your work.

3. Reasonableness — the ability to make reasonable, realistic, and informed decisions.

Commitment and productivity

1. Effectiveness — focus on the final result.

2. Perseverance — the ability to overcome the limitations imposed by the current situation.

3. Dedication to the organization and business orientation — willingness to follow the organization's standards, passion for work, and responsibility for the quality of their work.

4. Self-confidence — willingness and ability to solve extraordinary tasks.

Teamwork skills

1. Team orientation — understanding the need for joint activities and the ability to work in collaboration with others.

2. Contact — the ability to establish business and creative relationships with partners.

3. Sociability — the ability to use oral and written speech, stylistic and other expressive means, to influence partners and achieve mutual understanding;

4. Listening ability — the ability to perceive, assimilate, and use information extracted from oral communication.

An expert assessment of the importance of these key areas of competence for the successful work of the HR manager made it possible to rank them in the following order (in descending order of importance):

1. Ethics.
2. Sociability.
3. Ability to listen.
4. Ability to make contacts
5. Team orientation.
6. Good faith.
7. Prudence.
8. Performance.
9. Persistence.
10. Self-confidence.

11. Dedication to the organization and business orientation.

Let us reveal the logic of this historical process of organizational and cultural evolution. The technocratic approach, which is rooted in the philosophy of positivism, has been moved (the most famous figure in this approach is Fr. Taylor) in the practice of organizing production and labor processes in connection with the sharply increased need to improve the efficiency of large-scale production systems focused on the production of mass-produced products. The employee in such human-machine systems was treated as a "cog", and the problem of optimizing the functioning of such technologies was solved by rationalizing social and industrial relations and labor processes through the use of more effective control and remuneration mechanisms. The ultimate goal of rationalization is to increase the level of exploitation of all components (including "human material") of these systems.

The negative social consequences of this kind of rationalization, despite the increase in labor productivity achieved, especially in crises (primarily during wars), due to the introduction of elements of its scientific organization, became apparent in the second half of the 1920s and gave rise to a series of social experiments (E. Mayo's Hawthorne studies). Humanization of labor relations, involving employees in the discussion of issues related to their production activities, using the positive effects of group self-organization — these are

the most important principles of the doctrine of human relations. Its implementation for the first time gave the employee the status (albeit unequal) of a partner in relations with the manager and owner of the enterprise when it was necessary to resolve the most complex social and labor issues. Only the collectivist solidarity of workers, which finds institutional expression in the activities of trade unions, could guarantee this style of relations.

By the mid-1950s, the collectivist ideology of professionalism, which is characteristic of mass professions, became a brake on scientific and technological progress, since the widespread introduction of technical innovations displaced mass low-skilled labor. Stimulating individual professional development through the inclusion of mechanisms of personal interest and personal responsibility is the specific nature of the new approach in HR management, which became widespread in developed countries in the 60s and 70s. Its application ultimately aimed to increase the entrepreneurial activity of all employees and make the enterprise more competitive.

However, the focus on consumer motivation of the employee, and hypertrophy of egoistic morality led to an erosion of the moral and psychological climate of the organization, reducing the overall effectiveness of its activities.

Therefore, as an antidote, it seemed natural to return (in one form or another) to collectivist values that ensure a healthy atmosphere in organizations where employees are united in temporary and permanent working groups and engage in complex and organized joint activities. In the conditions of the deep structural crisis of the 70s, creating an optimal form of organization for such working groups, as a rule, from the point of view of solving unusual problems, has become a valuable task in itself. Social and cultural creativity of employees themselves, their direct participation in self-organization and self-management of joint activities, mutual control, mutual assistance and interchangeability, clarity of common values and goals that determine the behavior of each team member, collective responsibility for results and high work efficiency, full development and use of individual and group potentials — these are the components of a new approach in HR management. The project was developed in the management of the 80s -90s, which was called team management.

Thus, we can talk about four main paradigms in personnel management in the twentieth century:

- the doctrine of scientific organization of labor;
- the doctrine of human relations;
- the doctrine of contracting individual responsibility;
- the doctrine of team management.

Conclusion. Moreover, the latter paradigm is an organic synthesis of successive transformations that historically precede the participatory organizational culture of other organizational cultures. From this point of view, the absence of historically previous and modernized elements of all three organizational cultures — bureaucratic, organic, and entrepreneurial — in a particular national or corporate organizational culture

makes it very problematic to fully implement the doctrine of team management due to insufficiently effective organization of activities, inadequate moral and psychological attitude or (and) low level of professionalism. This determinism of the degree of maturity of the national and corporate organizational culture of applying advanced methods of personnel management in personnel management explains, in particular, the im-

possibility of artificially transferring even the most effective tools of personnel work to the practice of domestic personnel services.

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